

1 **The role of social costs as a mechanism enforcing the honesty of ultraviolet signals in a**
2 **lizard**

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15 **Short title:** Social costs of an ultraviolet signal

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 According to animal signalling theory, various mechanisms can maintain signal honesty in the
20 face of deception. Conventional signals are usually cheap to produce but socially imposed
21 costs, often taking the form of aggression from conspecifics, can enforce their honesty. While
22 our understanding of signal evolution and honesty has much improved for some pigment-
23 based colour signals, the mechanisms maintaining the honesty of structural colour signals,
24 such as ultraviolet (UV), remain elusive. Here, we used the common lizard *Zootoca vivipara*
25 to test whether or not the honesty of UV signals displayed on male throats is under social
26 control. To do so, we staged dyadic agonistic interactions between non-manipulated focal
27 males and opponents of either larger or smaller body size, and with either control or
28 manipulated UV signals so as to create small cheaters with UV-enhanced throats, large
29 cheaters with UV-reduced throats, and their respective controls. Focusing on control
30 interactions, we first confirmed that male UV coloration and bite force were good predictors
31 of contest outcomes in this species. Furthermore, in support of a conventional signal
32 hypothesis, focal males were more aggressive towards large cheaters and became more
33 submissive when these large cheaters retaliated, and were less submissive against small
34 cheaters. However, that focal males were not more aggressive towards small cheaters
35 contradicts our initial predictions. Overall, we provide some evidence suggesting that socially
36 imposed costs may enforce the honesty of UV signals in common lizards.

37

38 **Key words:** Animal communication – Deception – Social costs - Signals – Ultraviolet – Male
39 competition – Lizards – *Zootoca vivipara*

40

41 **Introduction**

42 Animals use an astounding variety of signals to communicate with one another and these
43 signals constitute the backbone of animal social interactions. To be evolutionarily stable,
44 signals must confer net fitness benefits to both senders and receivers and this condition can be
45 achieved only if signals are honest on average (Maynard Smith and Harper 2003; Searcy and
46 Nowicki 2005; Bradbury and Vehrencamp 2011). When the interests of senders and receivers
47 diverge, mechanisms enforcing signal honesty are required to prevent low-quality individuals
48 from dishonestly signalling high-quality (Searcy and Nowicki 2005). For example,
49 differential costs conditional on the sender's quality may be associated with the signal to
50 ensure its honesty (Searcy and Nowicki 2005; Bradbury and Vehrencamp 2011; Higham
51 2014). These costs may be a direct consequence of signal production and/or maintenance (i.e.
52 physiological costs Zahavi 1975; Grafen 1990; Higham 2014; Webster et al. 2018), or may be
53 imposed by receivers during social interactions, e.g. in the form of retaliation or punishment
54 (i.e. social costs, Johnstone and Norris 1993; Guilford and Dawkins 1995; Bradbury and
55 Vehrencamp 2011; Bachmann et al. 2017).

56 Conventional signals, sometimes referred to as badges of status in the context of male
57 competition, fall in the second category (Hurd 1997; Whiting et al. 2003; Bradbury and
58 Vehrencamp 2011). They are linked to the advertised quality based on an arbitrary convention
59 (Guilford and Dawkins 1995; Hurd and Enquist 2005) and are associated with socially
60 imposed costs (Higham 2014; Weaver et al. 2017). Tibbetts (2014) and Webster et al. (2018)
61 further highlight that physiological and social costs need not be mutually exclusive in
62 maintaining honest signalling and argue that, regardless of whether physiological costs exist
63 or not, social costs are likely to arise during aggressive interactions. This is because receivers
64 are more likely to attack when rivals have similar signalling level as their own (Tibbetts

65 2014), and/or when they discern a mismatch between their opponent's quality and signalling
66 level (Rohwer and Rohwer 1978). In both cases, cheating becomes particularly costly for low-
67 quality individuals because of the increased risk of injury due to physical attacks (Tibbetts
68 2014). In spite of this, most studies investigating honest signalling focused on physiological
69 costs and very few on social costs, thus leading Bachmann et al. (2017) to call for adequately
70 designed studies to reduce this research bias.

71 Colour signals constitute a diverse class of signals and result from different colour-
72 producing mechanisms including pigmentary and structural components (Shawkey and
73 D'Alba 2017). Recent evidence has much improved our understanding of the signalling role
74 and evolution of pigment-based colours such as melanin- and carotenoid-based colours
75 (Svensson and Wong 2011; Roulin 2016; Weaver et al. 2017; San-Jose and Roulin 2018). In
76 fact, most conventional signals described so far are colour signals (but see Molles and
77 Vehrencamp 2001; Vehrencamp 2001) displayed during male-male competition that involve
78 pigment-based colours, especially melanin-based black or white coloration (Møller 1987;
79 Martín and Forsman 1997; Qvarnstrom 1997; Beani and Turillazzi 1999; Ligon and McGraw
80 2016; Bachmann et al. 2017). Social costs can also maintain the honesty of rapid colour
81 change (Ligon and McGraw 2016), and of pigment-based colours potentially costly to
82 produce (Martín and Forsman 1997).

83 The costs maintaining the honesty of structural colour signals, including ultraviolet
84 (UV) signals, are yet to be uncovered. Some lines of argument suggest that assembling the
85 dermal, light-scattering nanoscale structures composing structural coloration could pose
86 developmental challenges, which could ultimately maintain signal honesty but robust
87 evidence is still lacking (Fitzpatrick 1998; Kemp and Rutowski 2007; Kemp et al. 2012;
88 Kemp and Grether 2015). UV signals have also been suggested to function as conventional
89 signals especially in lizards, but hard proof is still needed to confirm this hypothesis (Whiting

90 et al. 2003; Stapley and Whiting 2006; Whiting et al. 2006). Names et al. (2019) manipulated
91 the UV-blue patches of male common wall lizards (*Podarcis muralis*) during male agonistic
92 contests and found that males were less aggressive and more submissive against cheaters than
93 against honest males, thus rejecting a conventional signal hypothesis in this species. In blue
94 tits (*Cyanistes caeruleus*), three important studies suggest that the UV coloration displayed on
95 male crowns may function as conventional signals during male contests (Alonso-Alvarez et
96 al. 2004; Poesel et al. 2007; Rémy et al. 2010). These, however, are not conclusive since they
97 were designed to explore the role of UV signals during agonistic interactions rather than to
98 test whether social costs enforce their honesty.

99 To identify social costs of colour signals, researchers must experimentally create out-of-
100 equilibrium colour signals to simulate cheating individuals and examine whether these
101 cheaters receive more aggression than honest signallers during agonistic interactions (Ligon
102 and McGraw 2016; Bachmann et al. 2017; Names et al. 2019). In this study, we used the
103 common lizard *Zootoca vivipara* to investigate whether or not socially imposed costs
104 maintain the honesty of UV signals. Male common lizards display UV-reflecting signals on
105 their throat (Martin et al. 2013) that correlate with male quality (Badiane et al. in preparation)
106 and play a role during male-male competition (Martin et al. 2016) and female mate choice
107 (Badiane et al. 2020). In addition, UV chroma on male throat increases with age and body size
108 (Bonnaffé et al. 2018). Altogether, these results strongly suggest that male UV-reflecting
109 throats signal male quality in *Z. vivipara*. Furthermore, body size is one of the best predictors
110 of male contest outcome in lizards with larger lizards more likely to win fights than smaller
111 ones (Carpenter 1995; Fitze et al. 2008; Names et al. 2019). Here, we first investigated the
112 relative importance of male UV signals and body size during male agonistic contests, and then
113 determined whether or not male-induced social costs maintain the honesty of UV signals in
114 this species. To do so, we designed dyadic agonistic encounters between non-manipulated

115 focal males and opponents that were either smaller or larger than focal males, with either a
116 control (i.e. honest) or a manipulated (i.e. cheaters) UV-reflecting throat. Specifically, small
117 opponents were either UV-control or UV-enhanced so as to create cheaters of lower quality
118 (i.e. small) with high signalling level, whereas large opponents were either UV-control or
119 UV-reduced so as to create cheaters of higher quality (i.e. large) with a low signalling level. If
120 the UV-reflecting throat of male common lizards functions as conventional signals, we predict
121 that cheaters will pay the cost of their dishonesty in the form of received aggression from
122 focal males. We thus expect focal males to behave more aggressively and be less submissive
123 against cheaters than against honest opponents.

124 **Material and Methods**

125 *Study species*

126 The common lizard (*Zootoca vivipara*) is a small lacertid inhabiting humid habitats across
127 Eurasia (Massot et al. 1992). In our study site, adult males usually emerge from hibernation in
128 March. The emergence of females starts approximately 3-4 weeks later in the beginning of
129 April, depending on weather conditions, and marks the beginning of the mating season
130 (Massot et al. 1992). During the mating season, males chase away other males to ensure
131 access to females and there is endurance competition among males to find mates (Heulin
132 1988). Adult common lizards occupy overlapping home-ranges and are polygynandrous, with
133 both sexes having multiple sexual partners (Laloi et al. 2004; Fitze et al. 2005). Adult males
134 have a conspicuous belly ranging from yellow to red, interspersed with numerous black spots
135 (Martin et al. 2013; San-Jose et al. 2017). In females, ventral coloration is duller, from cream
136 to orange, with fewer black spots than males and extends more on the throat (Bauwens 1987;
137 Cote et al. 2008). In addition, the ventral and throat coloration have a secondary reflectance
138 peak in the UV, which is especially pronounced in males, particularly on their throat (Martin
139 et al. 2013).

140 *Sampling and measurements*

141 On March 19th 2018, we captured 59 adult males by hand at the Centre de Recherche en
142 Ecologie Expérimentale et Prédictive (CEREEP-Ecotron IleDeFrance, 48°17'N, 2°41'E),
143 where a captive population of common lizards is maintained in separate 100-m² enclosures.
144 We brought the lizards to the laboratory, measured their snout-vent length (SVL) with a ruler
145 (± 1 mm), and their body mass using a digital scale (± 1 mg). We also measured bite force,
146 which has been shown to be a good proxy for fighting ability and whole-organism
147 performance in lizards (Huyghe et al. 2005; Lappin and Husak 2005), using a purpose-built
148 bite force meter constructed from a modified Sauter 25N digital force gauge. We retained the
149 maximum score out of three bite force measurements and made sure that the lizards had a
150 body temperature comprised between 30°C and 35°C when biting, since their preferred body
151 temperature is around 34°C (Rozen–Rechels et al. 2019).

152 We obtained reflectance spectra from the throat and belly of each male (two replicates
153 per body region) using a USB-2000 diode-array spectrophotometer with a R400-7-UV/VIS
154 reading-illumination probe (Ocean Optics Inc.) and a notebook computer running OceanView
155 (Ocean Optics Inc.). We took reflectance readings in a darkened room using an HL-2000
156 Halogen-Deuterium light source (Ocean Optics Inc.) for full spectrum illumination. We
157 recorded reflectance spectra relative to a white diffuse standard (WS1; Ocean Optics Inc.) and
158 a dark reading. We set integration time to 9, scans to average to 10, and boxcar width to 10.
159 For data acquisition, we hand-held the probe over the centre of the targeted colour patch with
160 a 90° angle between the probe and the skin surface (i.e. coincident normal recording
161 geometry, Anderson and Prager 2006). An entomological pin attached to the tip of the probe
162 allowed us to maintain a constant distance of 3 mm between the tip of the probe and the skin
163 surface. We always aimed the probe at a skin area larger than 1.5 mm in diameter that did not
164 contain any black spot to avoid spectral contamination (Badiane et al. 2017). We later

165 processed spectral data in R v.3.3.2 (R Development Core Team 2017) using the package
166 *pavo* 2.0 (Maia et al. 2019). We cropped each spectrum between 300-700 nm, smoothed them
167 using a loess smooth span of 0.2, and averaged the two replicates recorded for each body
168 region. Then, we extracted two UV-related colorimetric variables from the throat spectra,
169 namely spectral intensity (i.e. $R_{300-700}$), and UV chroma (i.e. $R_{300-400}/R_{300-700}$).

170 Following measurement, we placed the lizards individually in opaque terraria
171 (25x15.5x15 cm) layered with soil substrate, and equipped with a shelter and a small water
172 dish. An incandescent bulb (25 W) and white light UV-B neon tubes (Reptisun 10.0 UVB,
173 Zoomed) provided heat and light following a 10/14-h dark-light regime. We provided food
174 three times a week (300-400 mg of live house crickets, *Acheta domesticus*) and water *ad*
175 *libitum*. Lizards were housed for a total of 18 days, including a 10-day acclimation period to
176 the laboratory conditions during which we waited the lizards' first moult to occur as it marks
177 the onset of sexual activity (Laloi et al. 2011), and an 8-day experimental period.

178 *Colour manipulation and behavioural assays*

179 Behavioural assays took place in a temperature-controlled room maintained at 21°C using two
180 neutral arenas to eliminate any resident-intruder effect (Martin et al. 2015; Martin et al. 2016).
181 Arenas were composed of a large opaque plastic terrarium (75x50x40 cm) with one
182 transparent wall to allow video recording, and contained a layer of blond peat as substrate.
183 Two removable opaque plastic walls divided the arena into two equally-sized compartments
184 on both sides and a larger compartment at the centre. The two compartments at the extremities
185 of the arena served as solitary holding areas to allow acclimation to the neutral arena, and
186 were each equipped with a 25-W heat bulb placed 15 cm above a shelter (Exoterra Inc.) that
187 also acted as basking spot. In the central compartment, we placed another 30-W heat bulb 15
188 cm above a wooden basking spot (12x8x1.5 cm). We illuminated the arenas with a light
189 emitting plasma fixture (Gavita Pro 270° GROW LEP) placed 80 cm above the bottom of the

190 arena. This light source reproduces almost exactly the full spectrum of the sun, including
191 UVB and UVA thanks to a UV transmitting glass filter, and is thus ideal to examine the role
192 of UV signals during laboratory experiments. White, opaque curtains surrounded the two
193 arenas at a 1-m distance to create visual isolation. Two digital SLR cameras (Nikon D500 and
194 Nikon D5300) mounted on tripods recorded the experiments in high definition from a lateral,
195 slightly elevated point of view, through the transparent wall of the arena.

196 To test the hypothesis that male-induced social costs guarantee the honesty of UV
197 signals in common lizards, we staged dyadic encounters using 59 adult male common lizards.
198 Each dyadic interaction was unique and involved medium-sized (56-60 mm in SVL), non-
199 manipulated focal males ($n = 29$), which faced opponents of either larger ($n = 15$) or smaller
200 size ($n = 15$) with control or manipulated throat UV reflectance. Small opponents ranged from
201 50-55 cm in SVL and were either UV-control or UV-enhanced. Large opponents (60-63 cm in
202 SVL), in contrast, were either UV-control or UV-reduced. This study design allowed us to
203 create a mismatch between UV signalling level and body size, and ultimately with male
204 quality since body size is a primary predictor of fighting ability and male contest outcome in
205 lizards (Carpenter 1995; Karsten et al. 2009; Baird 2013; Names et al. 2019). Focal males
206 were always 3-6 mm larger ($\beta = 4.21 \pm 0.41$, $p < 0.001$) and 1-5 mm smaller ($\beta = -2.84 \pm$
207 0.42 , $p < 0.001$) than their small and large opponents, respectively. There were no significant
208 differences in body size and body mass between small controls and small cheaters (SVL: $\beta = -$
209 0.38 ± 0.66 , $p = 0.978$; body mass: $\beta = -0.21 \pm 0.21$, $p = 0.846$), nor between large controls
210 and large cheaters (SVL: $\beta = 0.30 \pm 0.68$, $p = 0.991$; body mass: $\beta = 0.37 \pm 0.22$, $p = 0.465$).

211 To reduce the UV reflectance within the natural range of variation (Martin et al. 2016;
212 Badiane et al. 2020), we used UV-blocking (290-400 nm) inorganic agents (zinc oxide and
213 titan dioxide) mixed with a fat combination of petroleum jelly and liquid paraffin
214 (respectively, 6:4:50:40 for 100 g). Large males of the control group were treated with the fat

215 combination and large males of the UV-reduced treatment were treated with the fat
216 combination mixed with the inorganic agents (Figure 1). The spectral curve of this UV-
217 reduction corresponded well with the spectra obtained in previous studies (Martin et al. 2016;
218 Badiane et al. 2020). We applied both mixtures using a thin paintbrush on the lizards' throat,
219 from the tip of the jaw to the collar scale row. To enhance throat UV reflectance, we used a
220 light orange Edding 4500 T-shirt marker pen (colour code 016) that reflects in the UV range.
221 This marker is similar to those previously used to enhance UV-blue coloration in birds and
222 lizards (Kurvers et al. 2010; Rémy et al. 2010; Names et al. 2019), except that we used light
223 orange instead of light blue in our study because it better matches the natural throat colour of
224 male common lizards. To facilitate the marker application on the lizards' throat, we
225 dismantled the marker and pressed the ink reservoir so as to deposit a drop of water-based ink
226 on a plate, then we dipped the tip of a forceps into the droplet and spread it on the lizards'
227 throat from the tip of the jaw to the collar scale row. We then let it dry for a few minutes
228 before starting the experiments. Small lizards from the UV-enhanced group were treated with
229 this marker pen while small lizards from the UV-control group were not treated at all (Figure
230 1). As Figure 1 illustrates, our UV-enhancing treatment augmented throat reflectance in UV
231 but also in the orange part of the spectrum, and spectral shape looked somewhat artificial.
232 This marker pen, however, produced the best spectral shape of all the different marker pens
233 and paintings we have tried.

234 Each focal male participated to four dyadic encounters against four different males from
235 the four treatments (i.e. small cheaters, small controls, large cheaters, and large controls)
236 presented in a random sequence. We chose the opponent so as to standardise the size
237 difference between focal and opponent males, such that the largest focal males encountered
238 the largest opponents from both the small and large size category, and the smallest focal
239 males faced the smallest opponents of both size categories. We designed the experiment such

240 that focal males participated to encounters only once every two days, and opponents not more
241 than once a day. We performed a total of 116 trials during 8 days with a maximum of 16 trials
242 per day (8 trials per arena per day) during the activity period of the lizards from 09:00 to
243 17:00.

244 Before each experiment, we removed the participating males from their home terrarium,
245 manipulated their throat coloration, and randomly placed each male in one of the two
246 compartments of the neutral arena. We allowed a first 10-min acclimation period with the
247 shelters and basking spot in both compartments. After 10 min, we removed the shelters from
248 the compartments and allowed another 10-min acclimation period without shelters to force
249 them to be active but we left the heat bulb turned on for thermoregulation. After this 20-min
250 acclimation period with and without shelters (and without observers), the experiment started
251 as we removed the opaque walls to reveal the central area and immediately turned the heat
252 bulbs from the two compartments off, such that the only basking spot left is the wooden plate
253 at the centre of the arena. We turned the video camera on and left the room to prevent any
254 observer-induced disturbance. The experiment lasted 20 min as the two males behaved and
255 competed for the basking spot. Next, a single observer, blind to the experimental treatments,
256 used Jwatcher (Blumstein and Daniel 2007) to analyse the lizards' behaviours from all the
257 video recordings to avoid any observer effect.

258 We recorded each time a lizard performed any of the behaviours described in Table 1
259 (Martin et al. 2016; Names et al. 2019). We assigned a coefficient to each of these behaviours
260 to give more weight to the most aggressive behaviours (Carazo et al. 2008; Abalos et al.
261 2016) since they are more likely to be costly for the opponent. We calculated an aggression
262 score, a submission score, and an aggression ratio as indicated in Table 1. In addition, we
263 recorded basking duration, that is the time spend on the basking wooden plate, because males
264 competed over a unique basking spot. We also recorded the duration of wall-scratching

265 behaviour for each male. This behaviour consists of males scratching the walls of the arena to
266 try to escape and may be due to stress as a consequence of laboratory conditions. It may also
267 be triggered by a male fleeing from another male, so we recorded it as well. We also counted
268 the number of foot shakes performed by males (Heulin 1988) to explore their role during
269 agonistic interactions. Finally, we recorded the number of times a male adopted an S-shaped
270 postures, a behaviour that could indicate intent of aggression (Martin et al. 2016). However,
271 the meaning of these S-shaped displays has not been empirically investigated and this
272 experiment may offer some insights to its meaning. None of the contests resulted in
273 observable injuries and all males were released to their semi-natural outdoor enclosures after
274 the 8 days of experiment.

275 *Statistical analyses*

276 We used R v.3.3.2 (R Development Core Team 2017) to perform all statistical analyses. First,
277 to investigate the role of body size and throat UV reflectance during male agonistic contests,
278 we analysed only interactions between focal males and control opponents from both size
279 categories, thus excluding the cheaters. We used linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) and
280 generalised linear mixed-effects models (GLMMs) to test the additive effects of bite force,
281 UV chroma, spectral intensity, opponent body size, opponent UV chroma, and opponent
282 spectral intensity on the aggression ratio, the aggression score, the submission score, basking
283 duration, duration of wall-scratching behaviour, number of foot shakes, and number of S-
284 shaped postures. We included male ID and trial order as random intercepts. We included trial
285 order as random factor and not as fixed factor to avoid overloading our models. Besides, we
286 are not really interested in the effects of trial order *per se*, and controlling for trial order
287 seemed sufficient in our study. We used the *lme4* R package (Bates et al. 2015) to perform
288 GLMMs on count variables assuming a Poisson distribution, namely aggression score,
289 submission score, number of foot shakes, and number of S-shaped postures. For the remaining

290 response variables (i.e. aggression ratio, basking duration, and wall-scratching duration), we
291 assumed a Gaussian distribution and used LMMs as implemented in the *nlme* R package
292 (Pinheiro et al. 2019). We proceeded with a stepwise backward model selection; we started
293 with the full model including all the fixed effects and eliminated the non-significant terms
294 until obtaining the best model with the lowest AIC.

295 Next, to test whether or not social costs enforce the honesty of male UV signals, we first
296 created a categorical variable named ‘opponent size’ with two levels, namely ‘large’ and
297 ‘small’. We created another categorical variable named ‘opponent honesty’ with two levels,
298 namely ‘honest’ and ‘cheaters’. Honest males corresponded to UV-control males while
299 cheaters corresponded to manipulated males from both the UV-reduced and UV-enhanced
300 treatment groups. Then, we ran LMMs for Gaussian variables and GLMMs for Poisson
301 variables using the same response variables for focal males and random intercept as above.
302 We included the additive effects of opponent size and opponent honesty as well as their two-
303 way interaction, and the additive effect of bite force as fixed effects. For all the models
304 described above, we checked the model residuals for normality and heteroscedasticity. We
305 used a squared-root transformation for wall-scratching behaviour to comply with these
306 assumptions. All continuous variables assuming a Gaussian distribution were centred and
307 scaled prior to analyses to ease result interpretations (Schielezeth 2010).

308 **Results**

309 Regarding the analyses of the control male encounters, we found that males with a high
310 aggression ratio had a high UV chroma on their throat ($\beta = 0.32 \pm 0.14$, $p = 0.029$) and males
311 with a higher aggression score had a significantly higher bite force ($\beta = 0.25 \pm 0.12$, $p =$
312 0.030). In addition, focal males were more submissive against opponents with a high throat
313 spectral intensity ($\beta = 0.29 \pm 0.12$, $p = 0.020$). We also found that males with a higher bite
314 force tended to spend more time on the basking spot than males with lower bite force ($\beta =$

315 0.31 ± 0.15 , $p = 0.058$). Focal males spending more time performing wall-scratching
316 behaviours had higher throat spectral intensity ($\beta = 0.40 \pm 0.17$, $p = 0.024$). Finally, focal
317 males performed less foot shakes when they faced opponents with a high UV chroma on their
318 throat ($\beta = -0.37 \pm 0.15$, $p = 0.011$), and adopted an S-shaped posture more often during
319 interactions with opponents with a high throat UV chroma ($\beta = 0.73 \pm 0.21$, $p = 0.001$).
320 Statistics are fully reported in Supp. Info. S1.

321 In the second part of our analyses in which we investigated whether social costs enforce
322 the honesty of male UV signals, aggression ratio of focal males was not explained by any of
323 our predictors. In addition, the two-way interaction between opponent size and opponent
324 honesty influenced significantly the aggression score of focal males ($\beta = -0.34 \pm 0.12$, $p =$
325 0.004). In conflicts with smaller males, opponent honesty did not significantly explain the
326 aggression score of focal males (cheaters: $\beta = -0.15 \pm 0.09$, $p = 0.075$). In conflicts with larger
327 males, focal males were more aggressive towards cheaters than towards honest opponents (β
328 $= 0.18 \pm 0.08$, $p = 0.021$, Figure 2A). Furthermore, our analyses revealed that the two-way
329 interaction between opponent size and opponent honesty best explained the submission score
330 of focal males ($\beta = -0.75 \pm 0.16$, $p < 0.001$). More precisely, focal males were less submissive
331 against small cheaters than against small honest males ($\beta = -0.33 \pm 0.13$, $p = 0.012$), but more
332 submissive against large cheaters than against large honest males ($\beta = 0.56 \pm 0.11$, $p < 0.001$;
333 Figure 2B).

334 Moreover, none of our predictors significantly explained the time focal males spent at
335 the basking spot, nor the time spent performing wall-scratching behaviours. In addition, the
336 two-way interaction between opponent size and honesty best predicted the number of foot
337 shakes performed by focal males ($\beta = 1.19 \pm 0.34$, $p = 0.001$). Specifically, focal males
338 performed more foot shakes against small cheaters than against small honest males ($\beta = 1.11$
339 ± 0.31 , $p < 0.001$ – Figure 2C). At last, focal males adopted S-shaped postures more often

340 when they faced small opponents than when they faced large opponents ($\beta = 0.57 \pm 0.20$, $p =$
341 0.005 – Figure 2D). Statistics are fully reported in Supp. Info. S2.

342 **Discussion**

343 Our results revealed partial evidence suggesting that socially imposed costs may enforce the
344 honesty of UV-reflecting signals in male common lizards *Z. vivipara*. In support of this
345 interpretation, we found that focal males were more aggressive against large cheaters than
346 against large honest opponents, and were less submissive against small cheaters than against
347 small honest opponents. However, inconsistently with our initial prediction, focal males were
348 not more aggressive against small cheaters than against small honest opponents and were
349 more submissive against large cheaters than against large honest opponents. In addition to
350 this, our analyses both including and excluding manipulated males confirmed that male throat
351 UV coloration and bite force are important predictors of male contest outcomes in common
352 lizards.

353 In the first instance, we focused exclusively on encounters between focal and honest
354 males to confirm that individual traits that are usually found to correlate with male quality
355 were indeed good predictors of male contest outcome in our study. We found that both
356 aggression score and basking duration correlated positively with male bite force, thus
357 providing evidence that bite force is a good proxy of male dominance. Bite force has been
358 previously linked with male dominance (Husak et al. 2006), male mating success (Lappin and
359 Husak 2005), and male fighting capacity (Huyghe et al. 2005) in lizards. Moreover, our
360 results showed that UV chroma and spectral intensity of male throat both predicted male
361 contest outcome. First, male UV chroma correlated positively with aggression ratio and focal
362 males performed less foot shakes but more S-shaped displays when their opponents had a
363 high UV chroma. Although empirical evidence is currently lacking, foot shakes performed
364 during male-male interactions are thought to function as appeasement displays in lacertid

365 lizards, including in the common lizard (Thoen et al. 1986; Heulin 1988; Font and Desfilis
366 2002 and reference therein; Enrique Font, personal communication). If so, since UV chroma
367 is associated with high aggression ratio, we would expect opponents with high UV chroma to
368 trigger more, rather than less, appeasement displays from the focal males. Similarly, the
369 meaning of S-shaped displays is not fully understood yet but a possible interpretation is that
370 these displays are demonstration or threat behaviours (Martin et al. 2016) since focal males
371 performed S-shaped displays more often against smaller opponents. Our results revealed that
372 focal males were more submissive against opponents with high throat intensity on one hand,
373 but focal males with high throat intensity spent more time performing wall-scratching
374 behaviour on the other. It may seem contradictory if we interpret wall-scratching behaviour as
375 a submissive behaviour, which could well be the case, but it could also be linked with
376 individual stress unrelated to the opponent behaviour (de Fraipont et al. 2000; Rozen–Rechels
377 et al. 2018). Overall, regardless of the direction of their effect, UV chroma and spectral
378 intensity of male throat play a role during male contests, both from the point of view of the
379 signaller, as they correlate with the signaller’s behaviour, and from the perspective of the
380 receiver since receivers adapt their behaviour based on these signals. Therefore, our study
381 confirms the importance of UV coloration as predictors of male contest outcomes in the
382 common lizard (Martin et al. 2013; Martin et al. 2016; Bonnaffé et al. 2018; Badiane et al.
383 2020).

384 We provide some evidence suggesting that the UV components of the UV-reflecting
385 throat of common lizards may function as conventional signals enforced by male-induced
386 social costs. The story indeed becomes more complex than expected when we examine the
387 aggression and submission scores. On one hand, large males with UV-reduced throats
388 received more aggressions but also triggered more submissive behaviours in focal males. This
389 result suggests that, for large males, downplaying UV signals is costlier than being honest

390 since these large cheaters are more likely to be challenged by smaller males (here the focal
391 males). When the focal males challenge the large cheaters, the latter retaliate since, after all,
392 they are larger and more likely to win fights, and focal males end up being more submissive.
393 Hence, under this scenario, what seemed to be a contradictory result at first glance may in fact
394 be coherent and support the idea that UV signals function as conventional signals in this
395 species. Unexpectedly, small cheaters (i.e. with UV-enhanced throats) did not receive more
396 aggression from the focal males than their honest counterparts. However, that focal males
397 behaved less submissively against small cheaters aligns with the predictions of a conventional
398 signal hypothesis. Our results also revealed that small cheaters males incited more
399 “appeasement displays” from focal males than small honest males, possibly indicating that
400 focal males were less willing to escalate the conflict against small cheaters, when we expected
401 the opposite.

402 In the case of conventional signals, social costs are either imposed to individuals that
403 signal above a given threshold intensity or penalise the mismatch between the sender’s quality
404 or behaviour and its signalling level. Signal honesty can therefore be maintained only if these
405 costs exceed the benefits of cheating (Searcy and Nowicki 2005; Bradbury and Vehrencamp
406 2011). However, some degree of deception may still arise and pay off as long as the signal
407 remains honest on average (Adams and Mesterton-Gibbons 1995; Carazo and Font 2014).
408 Individuals can either be exclusively honest or exclusively dishonest, or switch from one
409 strategy to another according to the situation they find themselves into, depending on whether
410 the signal is very labile and can change rapidly or not (Akçay et al. 2013; Wilson and
411 Angilletta 2015; Ligon and McGraw 2016). In common lizards, the UV-reflecting coloration
412 on males’ throat does not seem to change rapidly (Bonnaffé et al. 2018), thus leaving little
413 room for “occasional” cheating. Retaliation or punishment rules taking the form of physical
414 and non-physical aggression are the main mechanisms maintaining the honesty of

415 conventional signals (Martín and Forsman 1997; Tibbetts and Izzo 2010; Tibbetts 2014;
416 Wilson and Angilletta 2015; Ligon and McGraw 2016). In this regard, the different
417 behaviours measured in our study do not have the same weight as evidence of socially
418 imposed costs. Our aggression score is the most meaningful factor here because it is the most
419 likely to inflict a cost (e.g. injury) on the opponent. Overall, social costs taking the form of
420 physical aggression may be quite high in common lizards, as 43% of our staged encounters
421 (50 out of 116) escalated to the point of a male biting another male at least once. Although we
422 cannot estimate the cost-benefit balance of cheating in our study, the risk of injury due to
423 physical aggression is high and should not be neglected in this species (Le Galliard et al.
424 2005). On top of this, other behavioural processes, for example in the form of non-physical
425 aggression and/or spatial dominance, not necessarily measured may increase the impact of
426 social costs. Our submission score may therefore capture the reaction to such behaviours and
427 give us hints on whether or not social costs exist. Similarly, other signalling behaviours such
428 as S-shaped displays and foot shakes do not directly inform us on social costs but may
429 provide insights on the contest outcomes, even though their meaning is not clearly identified.
430 Altogether, our results seem to indicate that cheating is generally more costly than being
431 honest, although we found some discrepancies.

432 In fact, the inconsistencies in our results involved almost exclusively interactions
433 between focal males and small opponents, as small cheaters did not receive more aggression
434 and triggered more “appeasement displays” from focal males. A possible interpretation may
435 simply be that cheating is more likely to pay off for a small male that exaggerates its UV
436 signal than for a large male that downplays its signal. However, in the context of male-male
437 competition, we would expect social costs to prevent low-quality males from signalling high
438 quality, and gain advantage in terms of resources and/or access to females over males that are
439 actually of higher quality (e.g. (Molles and Vehrencamp 2001)). Another hypothesis may be

440 that smaller males generally behave in a non-threatening way when they face larger males, for
441 example by avoiding being close to larger opponent. Therefore, focal males would not need to
442 show any sign of aggression and spatial occupancy, perhaps captured in our submission score,
443 may be enough to affirm dominance. Alternatively, if focal males are more aggressive
444 towards any opponent that signals above a given threshold intensity, and that small honest
445 males are already signalling close to or above that threshold, we would not see any difference
446 in terms of aggression score between small cheaters and their honest counterparts. However,
447 in this context, we would not expect to find differences in submission score as we did here.
448 This also raises the possibility that our results were obscured by our UV manipulation
449 protocol. While the experimental reduction of the UV reflectance within the natural range of
450 variation has been previously validated in the common lizard (Martin et al. 2016; Badiane et
451 al. 2020) and other lizard species (Martin et al. 2015; Names et al. 2019), it is much more
452 difficult to enhance UV reflectance. To the best of our knowledge, only a handful of studies
453 have experimentally augmented the UV coloration of animals, mostly in the blue tits
454 *Cyanistes caeruleus* (Delhey et al. 2007; Poesel et al. 2007; Rémy et al. 2010) and one study
455 in the common wall lizard *Podarcis muralis* (Names et al. 2019). In these and our study,
456 whether or not these UV-enhanced patches can be considered to be within the natural range of
457 variation remains debatable, since spectral shape can look artificial. In addition, our marker
458 pen did not only increase reflectance in the UV range but also in the orange part of the
459 spectrum and this may set a limit to results interpretations since we do not know how this may
460 have influenced the outcome of our behavioural experiments. It is therefore possible that the
461 focal males did not consider the UV-enhanced throat of small cheaters as a high signalling
462 level, but simply as an ‘odd’ signal. For example, the increased orange coloration on the
463 throat may somewhat resemble female’s throats (Martin et al. 2013) and thus confuse the

464 receivers. Future studies should investigate adequate methods to enhance “naturally” UV
465 coloration so that research on UV signalling may take a step forward.

466

467 In conclusions, we provide some evidence suggesting that social costs, mostly imposed on
468 larger lizards, may maintain the honesty of UV-reflecting signals in the common lizard. In
469 other words, these social costs taking the form of physical and non-physical aggression
470 participate to promote the display of honest UV signals in the face of deception. Our findings,
471 although not entirely conclusive, indicate that UV signals, and more generally structurally
472 produced colour signals, can be honest thanks to social costs imposed by rival males during
473 male-male competition. Future work should keep investigating these avenues of signal
474 honesty with UV signals to improve our understanding of animal communication at large.

475

476 **Acknowledgements**

477 We are thankful to Bruno Malhao for helping us build the two experimental arenas. This
478 study is part of the project UVSIGNAL funded by a Marie Sklodowska-Curie fellowship
479 (European program Horizon 2020) attributed to Arnaud Badiane. This work has benefited
480 from technical and human resources provided by CEREEP-Ecotron IleDeFrance (CNRS/ENS
481 UMS 3194) as well as financial support from the Regional Council of Ile-de-France under the
482 DIM Program R2DS bearing the reference I-05-098/R. It has received a support under the
483 program " Investissements d'Avenir" launched by the French government and implemented by
484 ANR with the reference ANR-11-INBS-0001 AnaEE France and ANR-10-IDEX-0001-02
485 PSL. The capture, handling, and experimentation on the animals in this study was authorized
486 by the Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation (ref.
487 APAFIS#19642-2019030616456029v4), and by the Direction départementale de la protection
488 des populations (ref. 2017-01666).

489

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699

700 **Figure legends**

701 **Figure 1**

702 Reflectance spectra resulting from the different UV treatments of our experimental UV

703 treatments applied on a single individual so that the spectral variations represented are only

704 due to the experimental treatments. Small cheaters were UV-enhanced using a light orange

705 marker pen. Small honest males were not manipulated. Large cheaters were UV-reduced

706 using a mix of UV-blocking inorganic agents and a fat solution. Large honest males were

707 treated with a fat solution only.

708

709 **Figure 2**

710 Mean and standard errors of aggression score (A), submission score (B), number of foot

711 shakes (C), and number of S-shaped postures of focal males according the opponent body size

712 and UV treatment. Aggression and submission scores were calculated by adding the

713 aggressive and submissive behaviours, respectively, weighted by their coefficient. UV signals

714 were reduced in large cheaters but enhanced in small cheaters. P-values are indicated.

715 **Table 1:** List and description of the different behaviours displayed by male *Zootoca vivipara*
 716 and their associated coefficient used to calculate scores.

Scores	Behaviours	Description	Coef.
Aggression score	Approach	Reduce distance with rival	1
	Chase	Quickly follows fleeing rival	2
	Lunge	Hits rival with closed mouth	3
	Retaliation	Lunge in response to rival approach or lunge	3
	Bite	Holds rival for < 2 s	4
	Bite hold	Holds rival for > 2 s	5
Submission score	Tail wagging	Wagging movements of the tail	1
	Burry	Number of times a lizard burry itself into the soil substrate	2
	Escape	Rapid movement away from the rival	3
Other variables	Basking duration	Time spent basking on the wooden spot	-
	Wall-scratching duration	Time spent scratching the walls of the arena	-
	Foot shakes	Number of foot shake displays	-
	S-shaped posture	Number of times a lizard adopted an S-shaped posture	-
Aggression ratio	Aggression score of the focal male / (Aggression score of the focal male + Aggression score of the opponent)		

717

718

719

